

STUDY OF VOLITIONAL QUALITIES OF STUDENTS
OF THE FACULTY OF SPORTS ACTIVITIES

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Annotation: The article examines such qualities of student-athletes as will, manifestation of will and personality. The main goal is to determine what affects athletes during training and competition.

Key words: students, will, manifestation of will, character, athlete, self-control.

Introduction. Modern sport places exceptionally high demands on the level of all-round preparedness of athletes [3, 5]. The most important elements of the training process are considered to be physical, technical, tactical and psychological preparation [1, 2]. Great strain of attention, complexity of motor skills, intense struggle, and in general all sports activities require great effort of will [4, 6].

Volitional qualities are manifested in the actions of an athlete aimed at overcoming difficulties and obstacles that are determined by the specifics of a particular sport. Any specificity of competitive activity requires from any athlete a high level of mental preparedness, strong-willed qualities, the ability to remain calm and emotional stability in important competitions [7, 8, 10]. This is precisely what underlines the relevance of this research topic.

Cultivating volitional qualities is one of the most important tasks in training a qualified athlete [9, 11, 12]. Indeed, in order to develop certain volitional qualities in a person involved in sports activities, it is necessary to proceed from those specific difficulties and obstacles that the athlete faces directly in the process

of his sports activities. Therefore, as mentioned above, any research aimed at studying the volitional qualities and volitional readiness of athletes is relevant.

Volitional personality traits. Volitional qualities are features of volitional regulation that have become personality traits and manifest themselves in specific situations, which are determined by the nature of the difficulty being overcome [9, 11]. A person can be timid, indecisive, impatient, not because he does not want to show “willpower,” but because he does not have the so-called genetically determined capabilities to manifest it, or, in simple words, he has fewer innate inclinations [12, 13, 14].

Before starting the process of developing the volitional sphere of the individual, you need to understand that you will have to face significant difficulties, so patience, sensitivity and pedagogical wisdom will be required. There are five essential conditions for developing the will [15].

The first and most important condition for this process is the formation of a worldview and the development of social feelings.

The second condition is mastering the ability to want. If a person does not have a clear understanding of what he needs, he will not be able to develop a strong will.

The third condition says that you do not need to make decisions and intentions that you cannot implement.

The fourth condition is the formation of the habit of evaluating one's actions, being aware of their consequences, and also looking at them from the outside.

And finally, the fifth and final condition for the education of the will is constant training of oneself in overcoming internal and external obstacles, constant exercise of volitional effort.

Among the volitional qualities, purposefulness, perseverance and determination, perseverance, determination and courage, initiative and independence, endurance and self-control are qualities without which it is impossible to develop all the

others. This is the quality of determination. It is a kind of basis for everything else. No activity will bring results if a person is not aware of the goal for which he is acting. The more effort required from a person in a particular type of activity, the clearer and more distinct the goal should be.

Volitional efforts and the readiness of athletes to demonstrate them Volitional conditions determine effective self-regulation and mobilization of human capabilities. Depending on the specifics of the difficulties that impede the realization of a particular goal in sports, volitional efforts acquire certain characteristics. For their manifestation, information is needed about the progress of sports wrestling and the state of the athlete's body, on the basis of which volitional self-control is carried out. It is also important for the athlete to consciously anticipate the reality of achieving the intended results. Volitional conditions only achieve high efficiency when they are subordinated to goals of various levels and meanings. The intensity of the manifestation of his volitional efforts depends on the difficulty of the goals chosen by the athlete. If the goal is easily achievable, the person will not show intense efforts, since it can be achieved without additional means. And vice versa, choosing difficult to achieve goals requires the athlete to demonstrate the volitional conditions for their implementation. A high level of aspirations, as a rule, contributes to increased motivation for achievement and, as a result, additional stimulation of volitional qualities.

Thus, volitional efforts can be characterized as an active manifestation of consciousness aimed at effective self-regulation and mobilization of a person's capabilities to successfully overcome difficulties in the process of achieving his goals.

In the end, I would like to note that a methodology was carried out to assess the degree of willpower. For the study, two groups were taken (a control group - students involved in sports and an experimental group - students whose students do not go in for sports regularly. Each group consisted of 30 people who were asked a list of questions (When starting a difficult task, do you try to think about the

problems awaiting you ? How do you usually feel when you get an unexpected call to your manager?).

As a result, the following results were revealed: in the control group, 24 athletes' character and will were considered quite strong, and their actions were considered realistic and balanced. 5 athletes also have strong character and will, and their behavior is quite responsible. 1 athlete's will and character are close to ideal. No person with a weak will has been identified.

In the experimental group, the results were as follows: 9 people with a weak will, 20 students had a fairly strong character and will, and their actions were balanced, 1 student had a very strong character and will, and their behavior was quite responsible in most cases. This is due to the fact that in the process of training a person faces serious difficulties, overcomes pain, instead of entertainment and other joys, he goes to training, which sometimes resembles hard physical work.

Conclusions. By performing various types of activities, while overcoming internal and external obstacles, a person develops volitional qualities that are of great importance for study, work and sports.

Revealing the meaning of will and the characteristics of volitional qualities, it should be noted that overcoming subjective difficulties and unpleasant experiences caused by training will certainly be replaced by a feeling of self-satisfaction. Systematic training and regular performances in competitions are effective means of an athlete's strong-willed qualities.

The formation of personality in sports is no less important than the targeted development of physical qualities and technical skills in athletes. The formation of a strong-willed personality in sports is primarily associated with the development of moral self-awareness in the athlete, which encourages him to achieve victory.

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